

SERPSTAT

All-in-one SEO platform

Title: How machine learning helps in building connections between departments: MQL and SQL scoring using neural networks.

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INTRODUCTION:

Visual assessments of crown marginal fit have limited use to assess marginal gaps on proximal surfaces. Other methods used in the literature to evaluate marginal accuracy on the proximal surfaces are with radiographs.

AIM:

To reduce the loss of revenue because of not used sales opportunities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A classical approach of MQL and SQL scoring systems was replaced by machine learning algorithms. According to interpretability limitations only a few types of algorithms were tested. The best result was obtained by using neural networks on each stage of lead scoring.

RESULTS:

The number of high paying clients was raised by 10%. The number of low paying client in sales funnel was reduced by 45%.

CONCLUSIONS:

In case of building MQL and SQL scoring system neural networks outperform other methods, including classical approach and other machine learning algorithms.

KEYWORDS:

Machine learning; Neural Networks; Lead scoring.

BIOGRAPHY:

Alex Danilin is a product manager at all-in-one SEO platform Serpstat. His previous career path from Middle SEO specialist to Senior SEO specialist and later to Analytics Strategist gave him an opportunity to work with different types of SEO projects including big international companies. So now he spends his time developing a SAAS platform that makes life of SEOs much easier.

Alex is an author of articles, a speaker at specialized seminars and conferences. He is interested in SEO, analytics, data science and Capoeira.